

The Project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb"

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Abstract: This paper presents the recently completed project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb", initiated as a pilot study for earthquake risk assessment studies in Croatia. The 2020 earthquakes accelerated the start of the project, making it a key component of disaster risk reduction strategies alongside post-earthquake reconstruction. The main activities of the project are described, with a focus on the most crucial part: collecting data (attributes) on buildings, which was necessary for developing the building inventory database in the GIS environment. The main risk metrics, based on the assessment in OpenQuake, are presented and discussed. The building-level risk model developed in the project underpins these results and provides a strong basis for future risk reduction efforts, as well as an example that can be adapted to similar urban areas worldwide.

Keywords: seismic risk; database; exposure; GIS; pilot-study.

1 Introduction

The earthquakes of 2020 revealed the significant vulnerability of the capital city of the Republic of Croatia, Zagreb (Atalić et al. 2021 2023), and a similar situation can be expected in other parts of the country, which are moderately to highly exposed to seismic activity (Herak et al. 2011). According to the latest census of the Croatian Bureau of Statistics, almost 20% of all housing units were built before the adoption of the first seismic regulations in the region, in other words, the buildings in which they are located were not designed for seismic action.

Continuous renewal of the housing stock, which, according to the Disaster Risk Management Strategy until 2030, should be encouraged, requires high costs, and the necessary foundation (the first step) of most strategic activities is a reliable seismic risk assessment. Moreover, this is a continuous obligation of local and regional self-government units, as well as of the Government of the Republic of Croatia, for the entire territory of Croatia, under the Civil Protection System Act. By joining the EU, Croatia assumed various obligations, including the preparation of disaster risk assessments. Although work on risk assessments did not begin only after Croatia joined the EU, it can be concluded that the issue had never been approached systematically or with sufficient awareness. This is completely evident when observing the existing data important for risk assessments, as well as activities aimed at risk mitigation in general (Atalić et al. 2019). It is important to emphasize that individual efforts and initiatives can hardly compensate for these shortcomings. One exception is the project "Earthquake Risk Assessment

of the City of Zagreb", aimed at a detailed assessment of the earthquake risk of Croatia's capital city, including the collection of data on every building in the city. The following text describes this recently completed project, which produced numerous valuable outcomes and, we believe, will truly serve as a pilot project for Croatia, as originally intended, and as an example for other areas of the country.

2 General information about the project

The project "Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb" was initiated as a pilot for a nationwide risk assessment of Croatia. It was carried out as part of the larger project "Multisensory Aerial Surveying of the Republic of Croatia for Disaster Risk Reduction Assessment", approved under the Operational Programme "Competitiveness and Cohesion 2014–2020." The planned duration of the project was 36 months (from April 2021 to April 2024), but due to various circumstances, the project ultimately had to be completed by the end of 2023.

The project's main activities included: development of a risk assessment methodology applicable to the entire territory of Croatia (1), definition of hazard in the City of Zagreb area (2), collection and processing of building data and establishment of a database (3), and earthquake risk assessment (4).

Within Activity 1, existing risk assessment methodologies, research projects in the field, practices of different countries, software packages and tools for risk assessments, and the legal framework were studied and analyzed. An earthquake risk assessment methodology with three levels of complexity was proposed, based on the availability of input data and the assessment team's capacity.

Within Activity 2, eight studies were prepared in the fields of seismology, geology, geotechnics, high-rise buildings, civil engineering structures, cultural heritage, and cartography, all aimed at more precisely defining certain components of earthquake risk. All studies are available on the project website (Potresni rizik 2020), and scientists and professionals from several institutions participated in their preparation.

Activity 3 concerned the collection of building data (using a building-by-building method) to create a new database (Figure 1). Since this was the most extensive project activity, it is described in detail in the following chapter.

As for Activity 4, earthquake risk was assessed for buildings and the population. A state-of-the-art methodology and the OpenQuake (Pagani et al. 2014, Silva et al. 2014)

software of the GEM (Global Earthquake Model) Foundation (GEM, n.d.), a global leader in earthquake risk assessment, was used. Earthquake risk was also assessed for bridges on evacuation routes and hydraulic engineering structures, but these will not be presented in this paper, nor will many other project elements, due to the paper's length limitations.

Figure 1. Building database.

3 Building database

The basis used to define the project task and the number of buildings included the overlay of three official/available databases: the Digital Cadastral Plan (DKP), the Register of Spatial Units (RPU), and Existing Land Use, to obtain initial information on buildings in the City of Zagreb, given that a Building Register still does not exist. According to the investor's project brief, 35 attributes (characteristics) were planned to be collected for each building. Some of them

include construction period (Figure 2), structural type, number of stories, regularity, floor system, roof structure, building footprint area, and gross floor area. In addition to the attributes required by the project brief, attributes necessary for earthquake risk assessment were collected in accordance with the methodology used by the GEM Foundation.

For the purposes of this project, a database was created, and the database model structure was adapted to the project needs. High-quality databases were identified as a critical issue in all existing risk assessments, and there was no database on which this project could rely. A well-structured database model was an essential foundation, but its value depended on the quality of the data it contained. For this reason, extensive efforts were undertaken by all project stakeholders to collect and integrate data from all available sources. Particular emphasis was placed on linking existing data within the city administration, since the risk assessment results are intended for practical implementation within operational systems. In addition to standard sources, the project used post-earthquake damage and usability inspection databases from the 2020 Zagreb and Petrinja earthquakes, national risk assessments, Croatian Bureau of Statistics data, state archive records, architectural and historical sources, and various city service databases covering occupancy, cultural heritage, and critical infrastructure. A large part of the data was collected through fieldwork (building inspections) and remote work (via computer). Certain data from the LiDAR survey carried out within the project "Multisensory Aerial Surveying of the Republic of Croatia for Disaster Risk Reduction Assessment" were also implemented (for example, building heights, roof slopes, and position relative to neighboring buildings). All collected data were entered into the database in the

Figure 2. Buildings by construction period.

required format by engineers employed on the project. It was essential to reliably identify the building type, the number of stories, and the construction period, as these are the key features for attributing fragility and vulnerability models to buildings.

4 Earthquake risk assessment – results and discussion

Earthquake risk describes the negative consequences of an earthquake (casualties, damaged and collapsed buildings, financial losses, and others) and the probability of their occurrence at a given level of seismic action. It is usually calculated using a set of variables, i.e., elements: seismic hazard, exposure, and vulnerability (Figure 3). For the risk to be assessed as reliably as possible, high-quality input data are required, and these data are precisely the elements of earthquake risk.

Figure 3. Elements of earthquake risk.

Seismic hazard in an area includes the potentially destructive effects of earthquakes (for example, ground shaking, liquefaction, etc.) at the observed location. In the earthquake risk model of Zagreb, the hazard model was defined based on a seismological study prepared within the project (Sović et al. 2023).

Exposure of the built environment refers to the extent of human activity in areas subject to seismic hazard. The most important part of exposure data refers to the inventory of existing buildings (the building stock), which significantly contributes to social and economic risk. The Zagreb exposure model was created based on the collected building attribute data. In the building exposure model, after cleaning the database results (for example, removing all buildings that still existed in the Digital Cadastral Plan but had in reality been demolished), there are about 136,000 residential buildings in total. The total replacement value of the building stock is estimated at around EUR 86 billion, of which about 37% relates to reinforced-concrete buildings and 62% to masonry buildings. Figure 4 shows the distribution of building counts by city district. Pie charts show the distribution of buildings by structural system material, with the following labels: MUR – unreinforced masonry, MCF – confined masonry, CR – reinforced concrete, S – steel, W – timber. As for the population, numbering just under 800,000, most residents live in reinforced concrete buildings (about 38%), while approximately 31% live in unreinforced masonry buildings and 31% in confined masonry buildings.

Finally, the structural characteristics of the building stock exposed to hazard are defined by the concept of physical vulnerability, which describes the susceptibility of exposed

buildings to earthquake effects (damage). In this project, the vulnerability of buildings was defined through fragility and vulnerability curves from the GEM database (Martins and Silva 2021). It should be noted that available data from literature must be used until region-specific curves are developed.

The assessment was carried out using the OpenQuake software package, which is used for earthquake risk assessments worldwide. Analysed risk indicators included financial losses, collapsed buildings, fatalities, and injured and displaced people. Risk assessment results are usually presented at the level of an administrative unit (here, city districts), not at the building level. Figure 5 shows some of the results of the earthquake risk assessment for a 500-year return period.

If the values for an earthquake with a 500-year return period, commonly used for the design of new buildings, are analysed, about 900 buildings are expected to collapse, and financial losses of around EUR 9.6 billion can be expected.

It should be mentioned that a deterministic earthquake scenario based on the 2020 earthquake, for which actual effects are known, was also used to verify the model. The results showed very good agreement for both financial losses and the number of damaged buildings. For example, according to official data, 25,528 buildings were inspected after the earthquake, while the assessment estimated that 25,400 buildings were damaged.

Figure 4. Total number of buildings by city districts.

Finally, based on the risk indicators presented, the most endangered areas of the city can be identified, as well as the building types that contribute most to risk. According to the assessment, the city's earthquake risk is high, due to moderate/high seismic hazard, high exposure (because of population density, cultural heritage, and the city's importance), and high building vulnerability (because of unfavorable structural layouts, age, poor maintenance, illegal interventions, and reconstructions). Certainly, the

Figure 5. Earthquake risk for an earthquake with a 500-year return period by city districts (total and relative values): financial losses in EUR (top) and number of collapsed buildings (bottom).

assessment results must serve city and state authorities in initiating risk mitigation activities, which are crucial for citizen safety, stable development, and preservation of the cultural heritage of the Republic of Croatia, as soon as possible.

5 Conclusion

The project “Earthquake Risk Assessment of the City of Zagreb” laid the foundation for risk assessments in the Republic of Croatia and opened the door to numerous activities that are expected to follow. Beyond providing a basis for civil protection planning documents, the project has created a valuable database and methodological foundation for setting transparent priorities in future investments aimed at reducing earthquake risk, with

strong support from the research community. Its results and guidelines are also applicable to a wide range of other crisis situations and hazards, extending their value well beyond earthquakes alone. As a pilot project, it successfully integrated available data and addressed risk from multiple perspectives, while also highlighting the need for continued database improvement and the active involvement of all relevant stakeholders. The importance of such a systematic approach is clearly demonstrated by the assessed consequences. If the values for an earthquake with a 500-year return period, commonly used for the design of new buildings, are analysed, about 900 buildings are expected to collapse, with financial losses of approximately EUR 9.6 billion. Overall, the project has established a strong and credible foundation for future

activities in disaster risk reduction and resilience planning in Croatia.

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